

QUESTIONNAIRE

PART A: RESPONDENT'S BACKGROUND

Answer each question by tick (✓) in the corresponding box.

1. Age

- 16 – 24 45 - 54
 25 – 34 55 - 64
 35 - 44 65 – over

2. Gender

- Male
 Female

3. Race

- Chinese Malay Indian
 Other, please specify_____

4. Marital status

- Single
 Married

5. Educational Qualifications

- PMR/PT3 SPM STPM/Matriculation/A-Level
 Diploma Degree Master/PHD

PART B: PRODUCT APPEARANCE

You will be asked about several aspects of “**product appearance**” in this section. Place a tick (✓) in the corresponding box to show how much you agree with each of the statements of “**product appearance**”. The number will be on a range of 1 to 5, with 1 indicating “strongly disagree” and 5 indicating “strongly agree”.

How to answer (example):

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

Visualization		1	2	3	4	5
1.	Color of a car. 	Bright				
		Dark				
		Color				
2.	The shape of the car. 	Round oriented				
		Rectangular oriented				
3.	Size of a car. 	Smaller				
		Midsize				
		Bigger				
4.	The texture of the car. 	Smooth				
		Rough				
5.	Logo of car. 	Warning				
		Safety				
		Common				
6.	The lighting of a car. 	Headlamps				
		Auxiliary Lamps				

7.	Rendering of a car. 	Photorealistic					
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8.	Style of car. 	Modern					
		Classic					
		Combination of modern and classic					

PART C: PRODUCT FUNCTIONALITY

You will be asked about several aspects of “**product functionality**” in this section. Place a tick (✓) in the corresponding box to show how much you agree with each of the statements of “**product functionality**”. The number will be on a range of 1 to 5, with 1 indicating “strongly disagree” and 5 indicating “strongly agree”.

How to answer (example):

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

Product Functionality			1	2	3	4	5
1.	Automotive safety.	Airbag					
		Dashboard					
		Backup camera					
2.	Automotive functions.	Voice-enabled					
		Car speech recognition					
3.	Brand-specific setups.	Steering wheel controls					
		Compatibility					

PART D: PRODUCT PRICE

You will be asked about several aspects of “**product price**” in this section. Place a tick (✓) in the corresponding box to show how much you agree with each of the statements of “**product price**”. The number will be on a range of 1 to 5, with 1 indicating “strongly disagree” and 5 indicating “strongly agree”.

How to answer (example):

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

Product Price		1	2	3	4	5
1.	Spare part easily to obtain in market.					
2.	Automotive components maintenance.					
3.	The price and quality of the car is reasonable.					

APPENDIX B Respondent Results

Part A: Respondent Background

Age

100 responses

Gender

100 responses

Race

100 responses

Marital Status

100 responses

- Single
- Married

Educational Qualifications

100 responses

- PMR/PT3
- SPM
- STPM/Matriculation/A-Level
- Diploma
- Degree
- Master/PHD

Part B: Product Appearance

Color of Car

Shape of Car

Size of Car

Texture of Car

Logo of Car

Lighting of Car

Rendering of Car

Style of Car

Product C: Functionality

Safety of Car

Function of Car

Brand-Specific Setups

Product D: Price

Price of Car

